

In vitro potential test of acetogenic bacteria, fungi and yeast as probiotic of green house gas reducer

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ABSTRACT

One strategy to reduce methane from the ruminant digestive tract is by microorganism manipulation in the rumen. Probiotic products could inhibit or reduce of methane production from the ruminant digestive tract and expect to increase productivity without negatively impacting productivity. The objective of this study was to examine the potential of acetogenic bacteria (*Acetoanaerobium notarae*) and Yeast (*Aspergillus niger* and *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*) and as a methane-reducing probiotic from the digestive tract of ruminants by in vitro test. The examination was performed by in vitro gas production with four treatments: P1 (control treatment), P2 (P1 + *Acetoanarobium notarae*) and P3 (P1 + *Acetoanarobium notarae* and *Aspergillus niger*); P4 (P1+ *Acetoanarobium notarae* + *Aspergillus niger* + *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*). Observations were conducted on the degradation of dry matter, degradation of organic matter, pH, total gas production, the concentration of CH₄ and CO₂, C₂, C₃, C₄ and C₂/C₃. The study was designed on a complete randomized design. Data were analyzed using ANOVA and LSD test. The addition of probiotics showed a significant effect on pH, concentration of CH₄ and C₂/C₃. *Acetoanaerobium notarae* and *Aspergillus niger* provided a better effect on the decrease of CH₄. *Acetogenic bacteria* and yeast had caused a decrease in pH than the control treatment. While *Acetogenic bacteria* and yeast (mixed of *Aspergillus niger* and *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*) affect the lowest of C₂/C₃.

Keywords: Probiotic, *Acetoanarobium notarae*, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, greenhouse gas.

INTRODUCTION

Through the methanogenic process in the rumen, methane gas is one form of loss of digestible feed energy in ruminant livestock (Boccazzi and Patterson, 1995), and contributes significantly to the effect of greenhouse gas. According to Johnson and Johnson (1995), this process results in 2%–15% loss of feed energy. Methods of inhibiting methanogens include: use of antibiotics; promoting viruses/bacteriophages; use of feed additives such as fats and oils, or nitrate salts, or dicarboxylic acids; defaunation; and vaccination against methanogens (Murmula-Meat, et al, 2011).

In order to avoid accumulation of hydrogen gas, another approach has been taken to suppress methanogenic process in the rumen, namely by homoacetogen bacteria intervening using hydrogen (Le Van et al., 1998; Lopez et al., 1999), where these bacteria use CO₂ and H₂ substrates for growing and producing acetic acid as a metabolite product. Bio-reaction of acetic acid formation through CO₂ reduction by H₂ is proposed by Ljungdahl (1986).

Reductive acetogens are a group of bacteria which produce acetate from hydrogen and carbon dioxides ($4\text{H}_2+2\text{CO}_2\rightarrow\text{CH}_3\text{COOH}+2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) using the acetyl-CoA pathway (Drake et al., 2006). This suggests that acetogens may serve as hydrogen sinks in experiments, which seek to lower methane emissions (Van Nevel and Demeyer, 1995; Morvan et al., 1996; Joblin, 1999) in cattle.

Chaucheyras-Durand et al. (1995) have shown that the presence of yeast cells could stimulate the use of hydrogen by acetogens and enhance acetogenesis in an experiment utilizing a co-culture of acetogen and methanogen. Mwenya et al (2004) reported that the addition of yeast culture to sheep feed was able to reduce methane gas production in sheep.

Microorganisms that could be used as probiotic for ruminants are Lactobacillus, Bifidobacterium, Enterococcus, Streptococcus, Bacillus, Saccharomyces (a yeast), Aspergillus and Propionibacterium. The common Saccharomyces that used for probiotic in ruminants is *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (Shin et al., 1989). *Aspergillus niger* is a fungus and often to use as probiotic such as *Aspergillus niger* and *Aspergillus oryzae* (Chen et al., 2004). *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* could also be used both as a probiotic for human food industry and animal feed. *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* is a probiotic microorganism which rich in enzymes, vitamins, and other important cofactors (Dawson, 1993). *Aspergillus* contains the cellulase enzyme which stimulates the growth of microorganisms cellulolytic (Offer, 1990).

Our hypothesized was the methanogenic process in the rumen could be reduced by enhancing of acetogenesis with a supplement of yeast and exogenous acetogens. Therefore, in the study, we examined the effects of acetogenic bacteria and yeast (*Saccharomyces cerevisiae* and *Aspergillus niger*) on in vitro methane production and rumen fermentation.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

Complete feed that contain commercial concentrate and rice straw with the concentrate : forage ratio was 40 : 60. Probiotic microorganism : *Acetanaerobium noterae* (liquid form), *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (dry form) and *Aspergillus niger* (dry form). Rumen fluid was taken from male PO cattle with a

rumen fistula. The cattle were fed with grass (kind of elephant grass) and concentrate with a ratio of 60:40. Artificial rumen buffer according to Menke et al., (1979), modified by Blümmel et al. (1997). Glass syringe for In vitro gas test and GC (*Gas Chromatography*).

Methods

Amounts of 500 mg of substrates were weighed and transferred into 100 ml glass syringe (Fortuna model, Germany). The substrates were added with 50 ml of rumen fluid mixed with buffer according to Menke et al. (1979) modified by Blümmel et al. (1997). The incubation was carried out at 39°C for 48 h. All of the measurements were repeated three times as replication. Gas production measurements were performed at 0, 3, 6, 9, 12, 18, 24, 30, 36 and 48 h incubation time. Sample for CH₄ and CO₂ production were taken at 24 and 48 hour after of incubation. CH₄ and CO₂ production were analysed using GC.

Treatments

P1 = control feed;

P2 = P1 + *Acetobacterium noterae*

P3 = P1 + *Acetobacterium noterae* and *Aspergillus niger*

P4 = P1 + *Acetobacterium noterae* + *Aspergillus niger* + *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*

This research was arranged on complete randomized design. Data were analyzed using ANOVA and Duncan test was conducted on the parameters effected by the treatment. Parameters observed were degradation of dry matter, degradation of organic matter, total gas production, concentration of CH₄ and CO₂, pH, acetic acid (C₂), propionic acid (C₃), butyric acid (C₄) and C₂/C₃.

RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

Table 1. In vitro rumen gas production profil

Parameter	P1	P2	P3	P4
Total gas	102.00±5.0	105.00±5.5	101.67±4.5	92,67±12.22
V of gas production (ml/hour)	2.13±0.1	2,19±0.11	2.12±0.09	1,93±0.25
CH ₄ (%)	1.67±1.93	3,79±1.53	1.48±1.17	2.54±0.65
CO ₂ (%)	0.83±0.49	1.11±0.40	0.59±0.09	0.89±0.17

Adding of *A noterae*, *S cerevisiae* and *Aspergillus niger* has no effect on total gas, rate of gas production, CH₄ and CO₂ concentration. Production is

closely related to the digestibility of ruminant feed ingredients (Nuswantara, 2009). The highest gas production on P2 was $105 \pm 5,50$ ml and gas production rate was $2,19 \pm 0,11$. The lowest gas production in P4 was 92.67 ± 12.22 ml and the rate of gas production was $1.93 \pm 0,25$ ml / hour. The treatment had no effect on CH₄ and CO₂ concentration. Adding of mixed of *A notarae* and *A niger* produced the lowest green house gases (CH₄ and CO₂). Adding *Acetoanaerobiumnotarae* was reported could reduce enteric CH₄ production and increase the composition of acetic acid in the rumen VFA fraction in vitro (Thalib, 2008). Adding *A notarae* mixed with *Aspergillus niger* on P3 showed the lowest production of CH₄($1.48\% \pm 1.17$) and CO₂($0.59\% \pm 0.09$) compared to treatment P1, P2 and P4.

Feed Degradation and Rumen Characteristic

The effect of the addition of *Acetoanaerobium notarae*, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* and *Aspergillus niger* on in vitro feed degradation and rumen characteristic were shown in Table 2.

Table 2. In vitro feed degradation and rumen characteristic

Parameter	Control (P1)	Control + <i>A notarae</i> (P2)	Control + <i>A notarae</i> + <i>A niger</i> (P3)	Control + <i>A notarae</i> + <i>A niger</i> + <i>S cerevisiae</i> (P4)
DM Degradation (%)	48.78±3.01	56.40±17.41	44,62±4.69	44,27±4.38
OM Degradation (%)	52.87±3.29	60.22±17.02	48.50±4.22	49.23±3,91
pH	5.92±0.05 ^B	5.74±0.03 ^A	5.78±0.04 ^A	5.78±0.04 ^A
C ₂ MI Mol/l	35.12±7.96	39.81±5.91	40.59±6.15	37.35±7.36
C ₃ MI Mol/l	9.90±2.84	12.33±2.08	11.67±1.53	11.87±2.80
C ₄ MI Mol/l	9.77±3.46	13.11±3,15	12.08±2.33	11.86±3.41
total VFA MI Mol/l	54.86±14.38	65.67±11.11	64.63±9.96	61.43±13.92
C ₂ /C ₃	3.56±0.24 ^B	3.13±0.15 ^A	3.38±0.09 ^{AB}	3.08±0.22 ^A

Adding *A notarae* and *S cerevisiae* had no effect on degradation of DM and OM, C₂, C₃, C₄ and total VFA. The range of DM degradation values were 44,62%±4.69(P3) to 56.40%±17.41 (P2). The range of OM degradation values were 48.50%±4.22(P3) to 60.22%±17.02(P2). The range of C₂ values were 35,12 MI Mol/L ± 7,96 (P1) to 40,59 MI Mol/L ± 6,15 (P3). The range of C₃ values were 9,90 MI Mol/L ± 2,84 (P1) to 12,33 MI Mol/L ± 2.08 (P3). The range of C₄ values were 9,77MI Mol/L±3,46 (P1) to 13,11MI Mol/L±3,15 (P3). The range of total VFA were 54.86MI/ Mol±14.38 (P1) to 65.67 MI Mol/L±11.11. Volatile fatty acids are end-products of microbial fermentation in the rumen and reticulum and, upon absorption into the portal bloodstream, become the main source of

metabolizable energy (ME) for the ruminant animal. The mainVFA, in descending order of their normal concentrations in the rumen are: acetic, propionic, butyric, isobutyric, valeric and isovaleric. The results of this study was different from those delivered by Hassan and Saeed (2013). They reported that *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* increased rumen VFA concentrations without affecting dry matter digestibility, can increase the production of C₃ in the rumen and lower methane emission.

pH of the rumen fluid was affected by the treatments. The lowest pH was at P2 (5.74 ± 0.03) and the highest pH was at P1 (5.92 ± 0.05). Hassan and Saeed (2013) reported that adding *S. cerevisiae* can increase pH in the rumen. The rumen's ideal pH is neutral. The lowest pH at P2 treatment affected by acetogenic bacteria as acetic acid-producing bacteria. The pH value is one of the most decisive factors to the microbial population in the rumen. Decreased pH occurs due to the rapid fermentation of non-structural carbohydrates, which will reduce salivary expenditure into the rumen.

Ratio of acetic acid to propionic acid (C₂/C₃) was affected by the treatment. The lowest of C₂/C₃ was in P4 (3.08 ± 0.22) P2 (3.13 ± 0.15) and the highest was in P1 (3.56 ± 0.24). Volatile fatty acids are important mid-products in the production of methane. Increasing of propionic acid production (C₃) always results in failure of methanogenesis (Ren et al, 2005), therefore the ratio of C₂ and C₃ could be able as good indicator for methane production. The lower ratio of C₂ and C₃ will reduce the methane production.

CONCLUSIONS

The addition of probiotics provided a significant effect on pH and the C₂/C₃. The mixture of *Acetoanaerobium notarae*, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* and *A. niger* provided a better effect on the decrease in CH₄ and CO₂.

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